

5-Aminoacridonium sulphabenzamide.—To a clear solution of 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) in alcohol was added a clear solution of *p*-aminobenzene sulphabenzamide (1.4 g.) in alcohol and shaken thoroughly well. After about half an hour, shining yellow crystals of 5-aminoacridonium sulphabenzamide began to appear. These were filtered and washed well with alcohol when crystals, m.p. 226°, were obtained. (Found: N, 11.6. $C_{26}H_{22}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 11.9 per cent).

5-Aminoacridonium sulphapyridine.—To a solution of 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) in acetone was added a solution of 2-sulphanilylpyridine (1.2 g.) in acetone. The acetone solution was concentrated at room temperature in partial *vacuo*, then diluted with water when shining light yellow needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 131°, were obtained. (Found: N, 13.9; H_2O , 11.3. $C_{24}H_{21}O_2N_5S$, $3H_2O$ requires N, 14.08; H_2O , 10.8 per cent).

5-Aminoacridonium sulphanilamide.—To 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) dissolved in rectified spirit was added *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide (0.88 g.) dissolved in spirit and shaken thoroughly. After standing overnight, 5-aminoacridonium sulphanilamide, m.p. 222° (decomp.), was obtained on diluting with ether as shining yellow crystals. (Found: N, 10.93; H_2O , 25.5. $C_{19}H_{18}O_2N_4S$, $7H_2O$ requires N, 11.3; H_2O , 25.6 per cent).

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A SIMPLE RELATION BETWEEN VISCOSITY AND SURFACE TENSION OF LIQUIDS*

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Newton Friend's equation ($\gamma = k\sqrt{\eta}$) has been shown to apply very well to the viscosity and surface tension data on a number of unassociated liquids belonging to different families. The constant, k , agrees with the quantity (Parachor/Rheochor) within fairly close limits as expected.

In contrast to the various complicated equations connecting viscosity and surface tension of liquids (Silverman and Roseveare, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4460; Buehler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 1207; Tripathi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 51) Newton Friend's equation (*Nature*, 1942, 150, 432; *Phil Mag.*, 1943, 34, 643): $\gamma = k\sqrt{\eta}$ between viscosity and surface tension of unassociated liquids is one of remarkable simplicity. It contains no arbitrary constant as k is given by the quantity $(P/R)^4$; P (parachor) can be calculated from atomic and structural constants, the same possibility being indicated for R (rheochor) as well (Bhagwat, Toshniwal and Moghe, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 29). In the present paper, the relation has been shown to apply very well to a number of unassociated liquids over wide ranges of temperature (Table I). Except for a few erratic cases, invariably at the lowest or highest temperatures, the equation fits in with data on most substances within 2 to 3%.

* This work was done in the Chemical Laboratory, Science College, Patna.

TABLE I

Liquid.	Temp. range.	k .	Order of % diff. between obs. & calc. values.
Octane	0—100°	285	4
Ethyl iodide	0—70°	365	2
Ethyl formate	0—50°	367.5	2
Ethyl acetate	0—70°	340	2
Chloroform	0—60°	355	1
Chlorobenzene	20—160°	390	4
Propyl acetate	0—100°	310	3
Methyl ethyl ketone	0—80°	360	2
isoButyl bromide	0—90°	315	2
Dioxan	20—90°	340	3
<i>p</i> -Xylene	10—130°	380	3
<i>m</i> -Xylene	0—130°	365	4
Acetone	—73 to 56°	400	3
Benzene	0—100°	360	4

In Table II, k is compared with $(P/R)^4$ in several cases. The rheochor data of Bhagwat *et al* (*loc. cit.*), where available, were used, parachors being calculated from atomic and structural constants. Considering that the rheochor data used are based on determinations at only one temperature, the agreement is satisfactory.

TABLE II

Liquid.	k .	$(P/R)^4$.	Order of % diff.
Ethyl formate	367.5	342	6
Ethyl acetate	340	342	0
Chloroform	355	378	6
Methyl ethyl ketone	360	378	5
Acetone	400	399	0
Benzene	360	368	2
<i>m</i> -Xylene	365	377	3
Octane	285	297	4

Table III shows typical instances (a good and a bad fit) of agreement between observed values of γ and those calculated with the equation, $\gamma = (P/R)^4 \sqrt{\eta}$. It will be seen that for ethyl acetate (good fit), the agreement is within 1% in most cases, while for octane (bad fit), values agree within a little over 4% excepting at the two highest temperatures where errors in measurement are most apt to occur. The usefulness of the equation in that it leads to the surface tension from viscosity at the same temperature (over wide ranges) or *vice versa* merely from a knowledge of atomic and linkage values of parachor and rheochor is thus apparent.

TABLE III

Temp.	$\eta \times 10^4$.	γ obs.	γ calc.	% D.f.
(a) Octane: $P = 346.2$. $R = 83.38$. $(P/R)^4 = 297$.				
0°	70.60	23.85	24.96	—4.4
10	61.59	22.80	23.31	—2.2
20	54.19	21.75	21.86	—0.4
30	48.28	20.7	20.64	0.3
40	43.28	19.6	19.10	2.5
50	39.07	18.6	18.56	0.2
60	35.51	17.6	17.70	—0.6
70	32.41	16.5	16.91	—2.4
80	29.71	15.5	15.21	—4.8
90	27.30	14.4	15.52	—7.2
100	25.20	13.38	14.91	—11.4

TABLE III (contd.)

Temp.	$\eta \times 10^4$.	γ obs.	γ calc.	% Diff.	
	(b Ethyl acetate :	$P=216.0$.	$R=50.21$.	$(P/R)^4=342$	
0°	58.25	25.50	26.10	-2.4	
10	51.20	24.36	24.47	-0.6	
20	45.46	23.24	23.06	0.7	
30	40.72	21.81	21.82	-0.0	
40	36.69	20.78	20.72	-0.3	
50	33.34	19.60	19.75	-0.8	
60	30.45	18.61	18.87	-1.5	
70	27.80	17.70	18.05	-2.1	

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OXIDATION OF ARTOSTENONE WITH HYDROGEN PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF OSMIC ACID IN EXCESS

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A monoketo-monocarboxylic acid of artostenone has been prepared both from artostenone and dihydroxyartostanone. Its oxime, anilide and semicarbazone have been described.

It has previously been reported from this laboratory (Nath, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 249, 71) that artostenone (I), the steroid ketone occurring in *Artocarpus integrifolia*, when oxidised with potassium permanganate in both neutral and acid medium, gives rise to the diketo-artostanic acid ($C_{30}H_{46}O_4$) (Nath, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1937, 247, 9). This also confirmed the hypothesis laid down by Windaus (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2008) towards the possible chemical changes in such process. Nath and Chakravorty (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 22, 19) have shown recently that artostenone forms an addition compound with hydrogen peroxide in presence of osmic acid, thus forming a dihydroxy compound (II).

It was observed that some amorphous powder was also obtained during this process, the yield of which varied with the proportion of osmic acid used. When osmic acid was added in trace, the yield of this amorphous powder was very low and the dihydroxy compound was obtained in abundance; while addition of the catalyst in excess gave rise to a greater yield of this amorphous powder. Hence, it was thought that the excess of osmic acid might have some effect in bringing about further chemical changes in the dihydroxy compound formed and giving rise to a new compound (III).

In order to verify this, the reactions were conducted with an excess of osmic acid on artostenone and also on the dihydroxy compound when osmic acid was added in trace. In both the reactions, the same amorphous powder was obtained which could ultimately be crystallised.